

Prompt Complexity Theory

Philip Mead

June 30, 2026

Abstract

In 1948 Claude Shannon's discovery of entropy allowed us to understand the total information content of a length- n string of digits to be the minimal expected number of bits required to transmit it. Taking the next step, Solomonoff, Kolmogorov and Chaitin (1960-66) defined the algorithmic complexity of a length- n string as the length, in bits, of the shortest program that, when run on a universal computer, outputs that string and halts. A canonical example is the irrational number π which as a string of digits has maximal entropy in the Shannon sense, yet in the Kolmogorov sense has a finite (and very small) algorithmic complexity.

The emergence of large language models (LLMs) has created a need for a measure of AI-assisted complexity, as the size of the smallest prompt or input required to generate the desired output. There are many pitfalls to this view. Evidently the models themselves contain information. Any model with memory that has seen the desired output, can trivially produce it with a small prompt. In addition, the smallest prompt, combined with the smallest necessary model, will at its lowest equal the algorithmic information. If H denotes the entropy of a string S and K the Kolmogorov complexity then

$$K(S) \leq \text{Prompt Complexity} + K(\text{Minimal Model}) \leq H(S) \quad (1)$$

However there are important implications of thinking in terms of prompt complexity. Consider building a codebase, if what you desire is similar to (or the same as) other existing examples, it can be reached with a very low prompt complexity. Or for example, you would like to create something like a user interface, which has thousands of lines of boilerplate code, but its functionality can be effectively described in 10 lines of prompt, its prompt complexity is that of the 10 lines (or less).

However, in other cases, the description of what your code does may not be much shorter than the code itself. In its upper limit, your code could be the shortest expression of the functionality desired. Crucially, if this functionality, or something similar, does not already exist in the corpus (and so an AI model cannot have prior knowledge of it), then the prompt complexity of that code is of similar size to the code itself. In other words, no AI will allow you to replicate the functionality of the code with a prompt substantially shorter than the code itself. The user will require full knowledge and understanding of the desired functionality and use of AI would be of (almost) no benefit.